

Exploration of Blending Teaching in Digital Image Processing for New Engineering

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Abstract: *New engineering construction has put forward new requirements for talent cultivation in engineering majors. In response to the current teaching situation of digital image processing in electronic information engineering majors, which cannot meet the requirements of the new engineering for the cultivation of engineering practice and innovation ability for complex engineering technology talents', to adapt to the requirements of talent cultivation, this paper proposes a blending teaching reform of online and offline digital image processing courses for new engineering. Starting from enhancing students' learning initiative and interest, the traditional teacher-centered teaching mode is transformed into a student-centered blending teaching mode, mainly focusing on teaching content, teaching modes and methods, assessment methods, and other aspects of teaching reform. In classroom teaching, project-based and task-based teaching methods are adopted, we adopts a multidimensional assessment and evaluation approach, which enriches the teaching content, stimulates learners' interest, helps students better internalize knowledge, and cultivate their engineering practice ability, innovation ability and scientific research ability, so as to improve the quality of talent cultivation.*

Keywords: *New engineering; Digital image processing; Online and offline blending teaching; Practical and innovative abilities; Teaching reform*

I. Introduction

The "Tian Da Action" New Engineering Construction Action Line points out the new engineering construction model, which aims to introduce the latest developments in industry and technology as well as the latest requirements for talent cultivation in the industry into the teaching process, updates teaching content and curriculum system, builds courses and teaching material resources that meet the needs of industry development, and connects the "last mile". By changing students' interests and methods, innovating engineering education methods and means, setting international standards at the forefront, and enhancing the international competitiveness of engineering education. In February 2017, the Ministry of Education issued a notice on conducting research and practice in new engineering, proposing to cultivate a group of high-quality engineering and technological talents with a broad scientific foundation, strong engineering practice and innovation capabilities, adaptability to the times and future changes, and adaptability to global economic integration through the implementation of the "new engineering" concept education, using new concepts, new thinking, new systems, new models, and new ways to cope with the new situation [1].

Under the background of New Engineering, electronic information students are required to keep up with the development of the times, focusing on improving their innovative thinking, continuous learning ability, and practical ability. With the rapid development of artificial intelligence, computer vision, and deep learning technologies, new theories, new methods, and new application of image processing continue to emerge, hot technologies such

as artificial intelligence and big data AI technology today have been widely applied in many fields such as intelligent manufacturing, visual robotics, medical imaging, consumer electronics. Digital Image Processing is an important core course in electronic information majors, with a close relationship between theory and practice. The course objective is to enable students to learn and master the basic principles, algorithm design methods, and model building methods and to cultivate students' systematic thinking ability, which lay a certain technical foundation for further learning in subsequent courses such as computer vision, machine vision, pattern recognition, and engaging in image processing related technical work. However, the current outdated teaching content, single teaching methods, emphasis on theory over practice, and single form of course assessment have led to traditional teaching models being unable to meet the requirements of the new engineering construction. Therefore, the reform of digital image processing teaching is urgently needed [2-5].

II. Current Teaching Situation and Existing Problems of Course

(1) The teaching content is outdated and fails to keep up with the latest developments

In recent years, with the rapid development of pattern recognition, computer vision, and deep learning technologies, digital image processing techniques have also made great progress. However, as an important core professional course in electronic information engineering and related majors, traditional digital image processing teaching mostly focuses on explaining the basic theories of textbooks, failing to keep up with the latest theories and technological of image processing and having a significant gap with practical applications, which greatly limits the cultivation of students' innovation ability, practical ability, and scientific research ability.

(2) Single teaching method, emphasizing theory over practice

Traditional teaching is mainly based on classroom lectures, with a focus on "imparting knowledge" and an emphasis on interpreting algorithms during the teaching process. Faced with abstract theoretical knowledge and complex formulas, students often play the role of passive recipients, with low levels of student participation and initiative; Due to the abundance of theories and formulas, it is easy for students to develop a fear of difficulty and learning, resulting in poor learning outcomes [6,7]. In the actual teaching process, most teachers focus on theoretical lectures, with insufficient integration with engineering. Students find it difficult to apply theoretical knowledge to solve practical problems in engineering projects, which contradicts the talent cultivation concept of implementing collaborative education between industry, academia, and research. Most of the experiments arranged in this course mainly focus on qualitative verification of classical methods, which lacks comprehensiveness, design, and innovation, making it difficult for students to integrate the knowledge they have learned, and lacks the ability to analyze and solve problems, resulting in difficulty propose solutions to practical complex engineering problems independently [8,9].

(3) The single assessment method fails to reflect students' practical and innovative abilities

The current assessment methods for image processing courses mainly consist of theoretical exams and experiment reports, without emphasizing on the assessment of students' practical and innovative abilities, resulting in insufficient adaptability to engineering application [10-11]. In order to actively respond to the new round of technological revolution and industrial transformation, and the continuous improvement of social requirements for the quality of engineering and technical talents, the positioning of

universities has undergone different changes. The teaching of digital image processing should be reformed and innovatively explored from the aspects of teaching content, teaching methods, theory, practice, etc. so as to stimulate students' maximum internal drive and enhance their practical and innovative abilities in engineering practice.

III. Teaching Reform of Online and Offline Blending Teaching

3.1 Integration and optimization for course content

The course group teachers have selected and optimized the course content and experimental projects based on the talent cultivation objectives of the Electronic Information Engineering major, and revised the teaching outline of the Digital Image Processing with a focus on cultivating students' practical and innovative abilities. The teacher has established a relevant course framework in teaching, which mainly includes modules such as image acquisition, image transformation, image enhancement, image restoration, image compression, image segmentation, image description and recognition. The teachers explain the basic knowledge points of each module in combination with the textbook content. For some knowledge points that are not updated in a timely manner in the textbook, they add some front lectures by experts in the field of artificial intelligence as the teaching content setting. Through the power of expert role models, students are inspired to bravely overcome difficulties, cultivate patriotism, seize opportunities of the times, explore innovation, and jointly build the realization of the Chinese Dream; The teachers also add academic discussion sessions, formulate relevant topics, then students organize content related to the topic through literature search. Finally, through discuss in class and integrate academic research ideas into the teaching process, which can enhance students' enthusiasm for participating in learning.

For teaching content of course experiments, teachers introduce new research achievements and hot research in the field of digital image processing as experimental themes, and divide the experimental content into two categories: basic experiments and comprehensive design experiments. Students are required not only to be able to write program code for basic algorithms, but also to develop practical application projects with MATLAB/Python. Students can develop their ability to analyze and solve problems by practicing engineering projects, which can actively guide them to apply the knowledge learned in this course to various competitions or university innovation and entrepreneurship projects. Among them, basic experiments require students to utilize the Digital Image Processing and Computer Vision Innovation Laboratory of our college to collect image signals, combine corresponding algorithms, to process the collected images by MATLAB or Python, draw experimental conclusions, and to analyze them. Comprehensive design experiments are not limited to specific experimental topics. Teachers design corresponding comprehensive project content based on the latest research results and the actual needs of society and enterprises for image processing application. Students are required to complete the entire comprehensive project through investigation and research, literature search, scheme demonstration, and program design processes to enhance their abilities of practice and innovation. Our course team has mainly reformed the teaching mode from the following aspects, and the teaching reform framework is shown in Fig.1.

Fig 1. Blending teaching reform framework

3.2 Online and offline blending teaching mode

The traditional digital image processing course mainly adopts the offline teaching mode with PPT. Under this teaching mode, students are always in a passive learning state with little communication and interaction with the teachers, and it is difficult to stimulate students' learning interest and enthusiasm [12], which is not conducive to improving practical abilities. So we will take stimulating students' learning initiative, cultivating practical ability and innovative thinking as the main line combining with "Internet +" [13] in teaching means, and build an online offline blending teaching mode of "online basic theory learning ,offline classroom discussion and analysis, project practice after class, and multi-dimensional assessment". The blending teaching mode of online and offline is shown in Figure 1. The entire teaching process is gradual from point to surface, which helps students accept and understand basic knowledge points, and guides them to analyze and formulate solutions to the problems to be solved in the project in class and after class, to simulate implementation, and explain and discuss in class. A Positive teaching system is built through active learning by students and guidance by teachers, thereby improving students' learning efficiency and teaching quality.

(1) Pre-class (online MOOC)

The pre-class mainly focuses on MOOC video learning. Teachers select high-quality teaching resources from Chinese university MOOC platforms, integrate relevant digital image processing resources according to our teaching knowledge points and teaching program, teachers also recommend MOOC resources to students with knowledge points as the core; guide students to enter the preview stage and complete the corresponding tests unit. Teachers use QQ groups for online tutoring. In the pre-class (online MOOC) stag, this project, we utilized the "Digital Image Processing" course provide by Shanghai Jiao Tong University to conduct blending learning based on MOOCs. Students first study the videos

provided in MOOCs online. We regularly pushed the teacher's PPT and chapter tests through the Rain Classroom platform, arranged regular Q&A sessions to address any questions students which may encounter during their study. To facilitate students' offline learning, we have fragmented the teaching content, segmented each chapter based on knowledge points, and emphasized the difficulties and key points of each chapter. We have carefully prepared PPTs and exercise tests, and uploaded them to the Rain Classroom platform.

(2) In class (offline classroom)

Offline classroom is an essential part of student learning. With limited classroom space, teachers mainly focus on discussing key and difficult issues to achieve efficient knowledge extension. On the premise of the "online MOOC" learning stage in the early stage, firstly, the teacher sorts out the knowledge points and provides students with a clear knowledge framework In classroom teaching; Next, students raise questions about the knowledge they have learned; Then the teacher answers the students' questions; Finally, teachers and students will provide their own explanations and discuss with each other so as to achieve the teaching goal of students actively thinking in the classroom.

In this stage, teachers can make flexible adjustments based on the difficulty level and application scope of the teaching content. For example, in the process of learning image smoothing and sharpening, programming implementation and processing effect display are used to guide students to solve engineering practice problems, stimulating students' learning interest and enthusiasm. Based on mastering theoretical knowledge and practical applications, teachers assign corresponding sub project tasks to the students. The sub project design mainly focuses on students as the learning subject, fully reflecting the organic integration of theory and practice, stimulating students' initiative and innovation ability, and improving their comprehensive ability to solve practical problems. Due to the different personalities and knowledge structures of students, group division of labor and cooperation can be implemented to enable students to fully utilize their talents and abilities; Due to the fact that smoothing and sharpening involve a lot of mathematical knowledge, are highly theoretical, and have certain difficulties, it is advisable to increase discussion time appropriately in the allocation of classroom time to enhance interest in exploring theoretical knowledge. This flipped teaching model effectively enlivens the classroom atmosphere, stimulates students' learning enthusiasm, and makes up for the shortcomings of traditional teaching classrooms.

(3) Summary and evaluation after class

By integrating modern information technology with MOOC and Rain Classroom for teaching, all teaching process data can be saved to form complete teaching process materials, such as online preview pre-class, interaction in class, attendance and testing, learning effectiveness, etc. Teachers download data and analyze it as the basis for process based assessment. Based on relevant data analysis, teachers also gradually improve teaching content, adjust teaching methods, and enhance the pertinence and effectiveness of teaching. Teachers download data to understand students' performance in the classroom, such as the number of interactions, questioning times, and test scores, in order to form an objective assessment and evaluation of students' learning. Teachers can also timely remind students who are progressing slowly based on the data, and can provide targeted guidance and countermeasures. By fully utilizing modern information technology and adopting a blending learning approach that combines online and offline teaching, the overall goals of the class can be achieved through multiple perspectives.

(4) Assessment method

In response to the needs of new engineering construction, a student-centered teaching system aimed at improving students' engineering practice and innovation abilities, which emphasize the assessment of course processes, not only assessing students' mastery of teaching content, but also enhancing their ability to think, analyze, and solve practical problems. This course focuses on process assessment adopting diversified assessment methods. When implementing the assessment, it is divided into two modules, with regular grades for 40% and final exam grades for 60%, as shown in Fig.2; The regular grades include five parts: homework (5%), experimental score (10%), MOOC learning (7%), group discussion and comprehensive training (13%), and mid-term tests (5%), as shown in Fig.3. In the teaching process, teachers fully tap into students' subjective initiative, improve their comprehensive ability to analyze and solve practical problems, in order to meet the needs of engineering talents.

Fig 2. distribution of score

Fig 3. Distribution of daily score

IV. Analysis of the Effectiveness of Teaching Reform

A survey and analysis were conducted on students, and the results showed that the blending teaching mode of online and offline had good adaptability. Most students believed that implementing blending mode based on MOOC + Rain Classroom would greatly help improve course teaching activities. The functions of pushing course, testing, and real-time evaluation in the pre class rain classroom are very useful. Overall, the blending teaching model of online and offline not only strengthens communication and interaction between teachers and students, but also helps teachers implement dual channel teaching. Teachers timely grasp students' learning situation. It shows that a good distribution of students' participation and performance in various aspects. Most of the students' grades in various processes are distributed between 85–90 , and the average score of the exam reaches 81.6, far exceeding the average score of the previous class and other courses. This indicates that the reform of the curriculum has achieved good results in teaching reform. The specific score distribution is shown in Fig 4-6.

Fig 4.distribution of process assessment

Fig 5.distribution of process, exam and total

Fig 6. distribution of Average Scores in daily, exam, and total

V. Conclusion

In the context of the new era and new engineering, the signal processing teaching team of the School of Electronic Information and Electrical Engineering at Yangtze University has transformed its education and teaching philosophy under the guidance of student-centered teaching philosophy. It actively carries out the reform of the "Digital Image Processing", innovates teaching content, integrates ideological and political elements, adopts a mixed teaching mode of online and offline, pre-class, in class, and after class, and combines multidimensional assessment methods to improve students' ability of analyze and solving image processing problems related to their major. The results of teaching reform practice have shown that blending teaching has stimulated students' interests and hobbies, mobilized their learning enthusiasm, enhanced their potential abilities, improved their ability of analyze, practice, and innovating complex engineering problems, and achieved the teaching goal of education.

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